

Electronic Warfare

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Electronic Warfare is defined as the set of actions that:

- a) Use electromagnetic energy to destroy, neutralize or reduce enemy combat capability;
- b) Seek to take advantage of the use of the electromagnetic spectrum by the opponent; and
- (c) aim to ensure the efficient use of own electromagnetic emissions.

Electronic Warfare can be divided, according to its objectives, into three broad groups: Electronic Warfare Support Measures, Electronic Attack Measures and Electronic Protection Measures.

Electronic Warfare Support Measures aims to obtain data and information from the electromagnetic emissions of interest used by the opponent.

Electronic Warfare Support Measures are characterized by the intentional irradiation, re-radiation, reflection, alteration or absorption of electromagnetic energy for the purpose of destroying, neutralizing or degrading enemy combat capability.

Electronic Warfare Support Measures seek to ensure the effective (active and passive) use of the electromagnetic spectrum, despite Electronic Warfare actions taken by the opponent, friendly forces or other unintentional interference.

Electronic Warfare Related Activities

The means of Electronic Warfare interact, even during the peace in the permanent search for the adequacy of its capacity to the constant evolution of the state of the art.

The absence of a real confrontation between forces means that the enemy's inferred ability must be based on intelligence information.

Therefore, the need for the Military to create a peacetime structure for the development of its Electronic Warfare capability is identified, with actions that ensure:

- a) Intelligence activity, so that estimates can be maintained realistic and up-to-date on enemy capability and support for friendly forces;
- b) Intensive training in the use of equipment and the development of tactics and contracts;

c) The evolutionary development of systems; and

d) the search and support for research and development in areas of knowledge, whether or not related to electronics, that have applicability to Electronic Warfare.

In this context, Electronic Warfare capability is gained through Electronic Warfare Readiness and Signal Intelligence activities.

Electronic Warfare Preparedness is the portion of activities that come from the cooperative sources of research, development, human resource training, and logistical functions of the Forces specifically directed to providing the resources necessary for the establishment, verification, maintenance and reformulation of Electronic Warfare capacity.

The Signal Intelligence activity, internationally known as SIGINT "Signals Intelligence", aims to obtain and systematically process information about the enemy's communications systems, electronic sensors and Electronic Warfare capability.

It has the purpose of meeting the demands of the Intelligence System of which it is part, allowing the correct dimensioning of the use of our own Electronic Warfare capacity, from the gathering of the necessary data, applied more automatically and efficiently during the tactical confrontations.

Graphic of Joint Publication 3-13.1 Electronic Warfare 08-02-2012

Divisions of the Electronic Warfare

Conceptualization

Electronic Warfare Support Measures It is the Electronic Warfare group whose purpose is to obtain data and information from the acquisition of electromagnetic signals of interest radiated by the opponent.

Electronic Warfare Support Measures form the basis of Electronic Warfare, and are the primary source of information enabling:

(a) a timely reaction to the identified threat through an Electronic Attack Measures and Electronic Protection Measures engagement or other appropriate tactical action; and

(b) the assessment of the capability of enemy systems and our own capability by further analysis of the data provided by SIGINT.

Electronic Warfare Support Measures Actions

Electronic Warfare Support Measures are conducted according to the following actions:

- a) interception search;
- b) Monitoring;
- c) Electronic localization;
- d) Analysis;
- e) Registration; and
- f) Diffusion.

These actions do not necessarily occur in the sequence presented, and may in some cases coincide with some of them, as they are difficult to separate functions in automated equipment, where human interference is reduced.

The actions of the Electronic Warfare Support Measures of interception search, monitoring and electronic localization constitute the acquisition of data.

Intercept Search is deliberate tuning over a range of frequencies or over a number of specific frequencies for the purpose of intercepting and recognizing active signals of interest, as well as making measurements of their technical parameters.

Monitoring is the deliberate monitoring of an electromagnetic emission of interest for a certain period of time to gain knowledge from her. Its basic function is to monitor the transmitted signal to verify the accuracy of the characteristic technical data that may have been obtained by a Electronic Warfare system or other sources and to raise new data of interest.

Electronic Localization It consists in determining the probable area of the target emitter by electronic means (receivers, processors and special antenna systems).

Analysis It is the process of examining the results obtained by data acquisition (search for interception, monitoring and electronic localization), in order to identify the electromagnetic emitters and obtain information of interest to the decision making process.

The analysis action works with the technical parameters of the signals, the operating procedures, the content and the location of the emitters.

Seeks to respond, with opportunity, to the needs of operations (immediate analysis). Signs of interest that require special treatment - more technical or time consuming (medium and long term) - will undergo further analysis (field analysis). Immediate analysis can be divided into five branches, namely:

a) Message Analysis - consists of processing the content of electromagnetic transmissions, in clear or encrypted, in order to extract the knowledge present in a message, raising evidence from of this knowledge. This branch of analysis applies only to communications broadcasts.

b) Traffic Analysis - extraction of data and information from the occupancy rate of the spectrum, the direction and the flow of messages, comparing them with the database.

c) Location Analysis - survey of the location of target emitters, assessing all aspects that affect their accuracy, to increase reliability, reduce the probable area of location of emitters and enable their tracking over time.

d) Technical Analysis - survey of the technical parameters characteristic of the radiated electromagnetic emissions, to compare them with the parameters of the databases, in order to enable the identification of the opponents who use them.

e) Final Analysis - coordinated meeting, consolidation and analysis of the evidence raised in the previous branches of the immediate analysis, along with knowledge about the enemy and the tactical situation.

In this branch, the locations of the enemy emissions are analyzed and, comparing them with the information obtained by the other types of analysis, one can contribute to the assembly of the opponent's Battle Order. Based on all the information coming in from

other analysts, it is possible to understand the functioning of the opponent's active sensors and communications systems.

The field analysis follows the same sequence as previously mentioned. However, it is recommended that it be done in a more controlled environment and with greater technical support. In addition, the end results are often longer and more elaborate.

Registration It is the secure, systematic and timely process of storing data and information obtained by Electronic Warfare Support Measures, in order to allow its availability for analysis and dissemination.

Dissemination consists in the adequate and timely dissemination of the results obtained, aiming at the availability of updated data, in support of decision making.

Product of Electronic Warfare Support Measures Actions are the characteristics of intercepted emissions are indicators that allow conclusions about the opponent, such as:

- a) Degree of threat;
- b) Position and intention to move;
- c) Situation and composition;
- d) Activities and possible actions;
- e) Technical characteristics of the electronic equipment employed; and f) identification of units.

Electronic Attack Measures Conceptualization

Electronic Attack Measures involve actions to prevent or reduce the enemy's effective use of the electromagnetic spectrum, in addition to destroying, neutralizing or degrading the enemy's combat capability, using electromagnetic energy or weaponry that employs the target's own emission to its enemy guidance.

It is important to consider that attacks using unintentional broadcasts such as infrared missiles and TV guidance are not currently understood as Electronic Attack Measures.

Classification Electronic Attack Measures are classified into two basic groups:

- a) Non-destructive (soft kill);
- b) Hard kill.

Non-Destructive Electronic Attack Measures (soft kill)

Are those that use the active or passive use of the electromagnetic spectrum to achieve the purposes of electronic attack without, however, causing any kind of physical damage to the opponent. They are divided into:

- a) Blocking; and
- b) Screening.

Blocking

These are Electronic Attack Measures techniques aimed at suppressing the opponent's use of the electromagnetic spectrum by interference actions known as Electronic Blocking, and by passive Mechanical Blocking methods.

Electronic Lock

Consists of deliberate irradiation of electromagnetic energy for the purpose of restricting or nullifying the performance of electronic equipment or systems in use by the enemy.

It is used to prevent or at least hinder the reception of signals on enemy detection, radio communication, electronic navigation equipment, electronic identification and weapon control and direction systems.

This block can be classified according to the execution method and tactical use. As for the method of execution, it can be classified into:

- a) Point lock - uses narrowband transmitters and precise tuning. It is employed individually over the bandwidth occupied by the opponent's receiver in the spectrum, and its efficiency depends directly on obtaining the exact operating frequency, which can be obtained by the Electronic Warfare Support Measures. The great advantage of this type of blocking is the higher concentration of energy in a narrow frequency range.
- b) Dam blocking - uses transmission of electromagnetic energy over a wide frequency range when compared to the bandwidth tuned by the opponent's receiver, denying or hindering its use.
- c) Scan Lock - utilizes time-varying narrow-range transmitters performing a scan at selected frequencies. The advantage of this type of block is the coverage of wide frequency bands without the loss of power density characteristic of the dam block.

All of the electronic locking methods described above have their employment conditional upon the situation, falling into tactical employment in the following cases:

(a) Self Screen Jamming. The units that employ it are themselves subject to the surveillance or attack of enemy weapons controlled by electromagnetic emissions.

b) Stand-Off Jamming - employed when the units performing it are not the primary target of surveillance or electronically controlled enemy weapons. This is the case of the blockade made by aircraft specially equipped for Electronic Attack Measures that, out of the range of weapons of the victim units, cover the actions of attacking aircraft; or cover ships, when they seek to block, electronically cover or support the main ships of the Force, which in this case are the real targets of enemy emissions. It can also be carried out by grounding stations with high blocking power acting on high-level radio networks.

c) Escort Jamming - effective blocking power is a function of the distance between the jammer and the target unit. When it is not possible for the attacker to produce sufficient blocking power over long distances, even taking advantage of the propagation conditions, a blocking platform will need to accompany him. Decreasing the distance from victim radar means that the power required to produce an effective block will be less.

Mechanical Lockout

Obtained when physical means are employed between a transmitter and its purpose (receiver or target). It makes the normal use of electromagnetic energy difficult by means of artifacts that do not transmit any radiation by themselves, only absorb or reflect it. The chaff, also known as windows, is the most commonly used type of mechanical lock and consists of small resonant dipoles that can be launched by grenades, rockets or other specially prepared devices. Each small piece of material acts as a reflector, returning echoes and, as a result, producing, on the locked radar screen, a jumble of echoes that can completely obscure the true target.

Screening

It consists in the irradiation, re-radiation, alteration, absorption or reflection of electromagnetic energy, with the purpose of inducing the opponent to misinterpret or use the information received by their electronic systems. What sets Lock Screening apart is basically its purpose, since the means employed can be the same. One of the effects desired by the Screening is to deteriorate the opponent's decision-making ability, which is a major aspect of importance in the tactical scenario.

Method

As for the method, screening can be classified into two categories:

a) Manipulative screening - is achieved by altering, absorbing and reflecting opposing electromagnetic emissions (eg Stealth Technology), or by covert emission of proper

signals (eg, generation of false messages), misleading the enemy by trying to interpret the data on friendly forces; and

b) Imitative Screening - This is obtained by introducing into the opposing systems signals that mimic their own emissions.

Means Employed

As to the means employed, screening can be classified into two categories:

a) Electronic screening - consists of screening performed by deliberate irradiation of electromagnetic energy; and

b) Mechanical screening - consists of screening by the use of physical means to reflect or absorb electromagnetic energy.

Hard Kill

Electronic Attack Measures are those that use active or passive use of the electromagnetic spectrum to achieve the purposes of electronic attack for the purpose of causing physical harm to the opponent. Destructive Electronic Attack Measures incorporate the concept of lethality into the Electronic War, which until recently was considered a defensive combat resource. They are divided into Targeted Energy Emissions and Target Guided Weapons Guidance.

Directed Energy Emission Consists of high power directed electromagnetic emission capable of damaging the opponent (eg electromagnetic pump and high power laser beam).

Target Emission Weapon Guidance Consists of the use of proprietary sensor weapon systems that exploit the electromagnetic energy radiated by the target during the guiding phase to destroy opposing systems and platforms (eg anti-missiles). - radiation).

Target Emission Weapon Guidance

Consists of employing self-sensing weapon systems that exploit the electromagnetic energy radiated by the target during the guiding phase to destroy opposing systems and platforms (eg anti-radiation missiles). .

Electronic Protection Measures

Conceptualization Electronic Protection Measures are the part of Electronic Warfare that encompasses actions that ensure the effective (active and passive) use of the electromagnetic spectrum, regardless of Electronic Warfare actions undertaken by the opponent, friendly forces, or forms of unintended interference.

Types of Electronic Protection Measures

The Electronic Protection Measures are divided, in purpose, into Electronic Warfare Support and anti- Electronic Attack Measures

The purpose of anti- Electronic Warfare Support Electronic Protection Measures is to deny the enemy the interception, monitoring, electronic tracking and analysis of our emissions through their Electronic Warfare Support.

Electronic Protection Measures and Anti- Electronic Attack Measures aim to minimize the effect of enemy Electronic Attack Measures or the side effects of friendly forces' use of Electronic Attack Measures on our equipment.

The following actions are required for the execution of the Management of Electromagnetic Irradiations:

a) Management of Electromagnetic Irradiations – Its basic principle within the prevailing conditions of electromagnetic propagation, is to ensure the use of the electromagnetic spectrum by our units and the friendly forces.

It consists of actions that have the following purposes:

1) control the emissions of the equipment itself, with the purpose of preventing the detection by the enemy of the electromagnetic signals emitted (Control of Electromagnetic Irradiations); and

2) Plan, coordinate and supervise the use of the electromagnetic spectrum in order to avoid or reduce mutual interference (Frequency Control).

b) Technical Resources - is the use of electronic protection resources, designed specifically for this purpose or not, existing in the systems of friendly forces, which protect them from enemy Electronic Warfare Support Measures and Electronic Attack Measures actions.

c) Operating Procedures · consist of actions to:

1) increase the reliability and safety of emissions; and 2) to prevent, retard or hinder the use of the Electronic Warfare Support Measures and Electronic Attack Measures by the opponent through manoeuvring and force deployment.

Organization of Intelligence Support to Electronic Warfare Operations

National-Level Intelligence Organizations

At the national level, organizations and agencies such as the Central Intelligence Agency, National Security Agency/Central Security Service, National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency, and Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA) are constantly seeking to identify, catalog, and update the electronic order of battle of identified or potential adversaries; analyzing and providing products on adversary electronic warfare (EW) doctrine and tactics; and providing much of the intelligence that is gathered about adversary electronic infrastructure.

Department of Defense (DOD)-Level Organizations

DIA is the lead DOD intelligence organization for coordinating intelligence support to meet combatant command requirements. Theater joint intelligence operations centers (JIOCs) will fully integrate all appropriate intelligence capabilities, e.g., planning, collection, exploitation, analysis, disclosure, disseminating, and intelligence support to EW and information operations (IO).

Combatant Command

At the combatant command level, the JIOC responds to theater-level EW intelligence requirements and forwards requests that require national-level assets to the National Military Joint Intelligence Center or other national-level organizations according to established procedures.

Subordinate Joint Force

Within the context of a geographic combatant command, individual subordinate intelligence directorate of a joint staff (J-2) organizational structures will be situation- and mission-dependent. The J-2 normally assigns one or more members of the staff to act as a liaison between the J-2 section and the IO cell where EW planners are normally assigned. This is to coordinate collection requirements and analytical support for compartmented and noncompartmented IO.

Graphic of Joint Publication 3-13.1 Electronic Warfare 08-02-2012

The planning of a Combined Operation can be conducted at the strategic, operational and tactical levels, having special characteristics due to the heterogeneity of the employment processes and the technical-professional peculiarities of the contracted forces.

The Head of the Intelligence Section is responsible for:

- a) Preparing the Situation Examination (Preliminary and Current);
- b) Collaborate with the Operations Section in the preparation of war action planning, specifically with regard to Electronic Warfare and Intelligence support;
- c) Prepare, together with the Operations Section, the planning of SAR Combat Missions, specifically in Electronic Warfare actions and Intelligence support;

- d) Keep the Battle Orders (naval, ground, air and electronic) up to date for the accomplishment of the mission;
- e) Elaborate the Signal Intelligence Plan;
- f) Prepare the Control Plan for Electromagnetic Irradiations; and
- g) Elaborate the Electronic Recognition Plan.

The Head of the Command and Control Section shall:

- (a) Structure, specify, install and keep up to date all electronic systems of interest to the combined command;
- b) Collaborate with the Operations Section in the preparation of the planning of IO actions, specifically with regard to Electronic Protection Measures;
- c) Collaborate with the Intelligence Section in the preparation of the Combined Command Electromagnetic Irradiation Control Plan, and Combined Command Campaign Plan, covering the periods, frequencies and application sectors of each sensor involved in each action; and
- d) Estimate the need for personnel and material related to the actions and ensure the capacity of human resources and the availability of equipment employed in radar and communications sites to ensure the effective use of electromagnetic spectrum during Electronic Warfare employment by friendly or enemy forces.

The way Combined Commands and Component Forces are organized to plan and execute Electronic Warfare is determined by their Commander.

Electronic Warfare has operational implications for planning and oversight functions that are typically divided among the various components of the Joint Force Staff.

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